

**METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG CHILDREN AND
THEIR INNOVATIVE APPROACH.**

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ANNOTATION

Many theories have been developed about what methods and approaches to rely on when teaching a foreign language to young children. Today, one of the main tasks of a pedagogue is to use a number of modern methods and methods in teaching a foreign language, especially English, at the lower levels of education.

Key words: preschool education, modern pedagogy, foreign language, method, approach, TPR, skills, competence, psychology

INTRODUCTION

The earlier language learning starts, the higher the level of language acquisition. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be said that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of words, but memorize them mechanically. In this regard, teaching children a foreign language has its own methods and approaches. Because the task of modern pedagogy is to search and create complex and unique methods that have a harmonious effect on all areas of child development.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Based on the psychological, didactic, practical, educational foundations of a foreign language, several scientists have expressed their opinions (I. V. Rakhmanov, G. Kh. Bakiyeva, G. T. Makhkamova, F. R. Kadirova, V. S. Setlin, J. J. Jalolov, T. Q. Sattorov and others). Nevertheless, there are not enough scientific studies on teaching foreign languages, including English, to children in preschool educational institutions in our country. Therefore, during the scientific research, a number of scientific research works on the issue of teaching children a foreign language from a young age were studied. For example, formation of children's oral speech skills in Russian through didactic games in an Uzbek kindergarten (F.R. Kadirova), formation of oral speech skills and competences of children in a foreign language before school (5-6

years old) (G.T. Makhkamova), scientific and methodological development of foreign language teaching in early education and issues of critical learning (N.N. Achkasova, O.A. Osiyanova, N.A. Malkina, O.A. Denisenko, B. Cheptsova, etc.), teaching methods (N. N. Achkasova, N. A. Yatsenko, etc.) were familiarized with their scientific works. The following works were selected from them: psychological approaches to the formation of communication skills in educators of preschool educational institutions (Negnevitskaya Ye.N.), the basics of teaching a foreign language to children of preschool educational institutions (Koliyeva N.F., Grigoreva V.V.), preschool education types of exercises used in teaching a foreign language to children of educational institutions (R.A. Dolnikova), methods of teaching a foreign language to kindergarten children (Futerman Z.Ya.; Chistyakova T.A.), foreign language games for children of preschool educational institutions features of teaching through (Ponimatkova.P), the methodology of using English literature in teaching English from a young age (Denisenko O.A.), teaching communication to 6-7-year-old children through scripted roles (Rebakova N.V.) and preschool educational organizations among them are the formation of oral speech using fairy tales for children (Malkina N.A.). Teaching a foreign language to children from a young age through a communicative approach. Work features A.A. Leontyeva, V.G. Kostomarov, O.D. Mitrofanov was manifested in the works of others. In addition, it was noted that the fluency of the pedagogue's speech is important in teaching a foreign language to preschool children. According to A. Zimnyaya, children should learn a foreign language based on their native language experiences during the educational process, only then it will be easier to remember foreign words [1]. According to Professor N. A. Bonk, when teaching a foreign language to a young child, it is necessary to take into account their psychology, because the young learner is curious and does not like to be bored. Therefore, it is appropriate to use topics that are close to kindergarten children. These are toys, animals, family, home, kindergarten, etc. The early education process motivates the children of preschool educational organizations to learn a foreign language in depth, which allows them to ensure fluency in their speech in the future [2].

K.D. According to Ushinsky, a young child learns to speak a foreign language better in a few months than in years like an adult. According to this scientist, learning a foreign language helps to achieve the following goals. The first goal is to get acquainted with the creativity of the people who are learning the language. The second is to expand the range of logical thinking, because learning a language has a

positive effect on human brain activity and develops it in all aspects. The third goal is to get to know the culture of this people and to be able to easily communicate with them. The next thing is to develop the skills to be able to write letters with the people of this foreign country easily in their own language [3].

As Rihon (1999) points out, more important than teaching young children is to consider the conditions that youth education programs offer. These include extra- and intra-classroom settings (eg social, cultural and economic value of language). According to him, my little boy's place to study

- Natural
- Contextual and part of the same story
- Fun and cute
- Relevant
- Social
- Belongs to a child
- Aimed at one goal for the child
- Based on what the child already knows
- Properly supported
- It was part of a coherent whole
- Multi-touch
- Active and experienced
- Memorable
- Designed to provide personalized, varied responses and multiple intelligences
- Should be in a free and warm learning environment. [4]

RESULTS

Teaching language to preschool children should not be done as a chore, but as a fun, enjoyable and natural daily activity, and this requires teaching using several effective methods. Below we will consider such methods:

Total Physical Response, or TPR, was created by American psychologist Dr. James Asher and is based on his experience of how people learn their first language. For example, while children are learning their mother tongue, their parents and caregivers are physically active in language learning. They point and give instructions and the child responds in kind. No one asks very young children to speak: only to listen and understand. As a result, children acquire additional languages along with the method of learning their mother tongue. Therefore, the idea of TPR, in short, is to create a connection between speech and action. Why TPR (Total Physical Response) has so many benefits, especially for new language learners and young learners. The combination of movement with language makes for naturally effective learning. Students actively use the left and right parts of the brain. It improves students' listening skills. Students do not have to speak until they are ready, so a "safe zone" is created, which greatly reduces stress. Kinesthetic learners (those who respond best to physical activity) and visual learners (those who learn best with visual cues) benefit most from TPR. (This is another reason why it's important to know your students' personalities and learning types.) Because no one is singled out, TPR is great for introverted students. The main way to use common physical response in the classroom: The teacher performs the action, shows it and says it (for example, "I brush my teeth"). Be prepared to exaggerate, use gestures, facial expressions, and props if necessary. Students will have to repeat the action.

Last Man Standing This is a quick game. But it gives readers some time to think. This game encourages cooperative learning, meaning that while other students are talking, the rest of the children are thinking of words themselves. A ball is required to play this game, and all students must stand in a circle. You will need to choose a topic of your choice. For example: Things found in a kitchen, food, profession, etc. The game starts by throwing the ball to a student. That student says an English word about the topic and throws the ball to the next student. Each student who receives the ball will have to say a word related to this topic. If they repeat the words they were told or can't find the words within a few seconds, they leave the game and watch the game sitting down.

Pictionary- Many English speakers are familiar with Pictionary, a drawing game. For the purpose of drawing, you can use a regular whiteboard or a white magnetic board. Divide the class into 2 groups and draw a chart on one side of the board for each team. You will write down the scores of the teams here. One person from team A comes out. And chooses one of many upside down words and draws that word on the board. And others will have to find it. The team that guesses the word correctly first gets a point. The team with 10 points is the winner.

It should be noted that teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible. You can use the following methods to teach English to children in a meaningful and interesting way:

- to teach by means of songs and poems the letters or combinations that are difficult to explain or remember, that do not have meaning.

For example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it.

- games related to mental and physical activities;

- cartoons; Although children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

- role play, the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: if one student shows the howl of a dog, the meow of a cat, the growl of a lion, another student needs to find out which animal these sounds belong to and say its English name.

- subject environment; Children learn the language well only if the teacher creates an environment suitable for the subject. For example: traveling, cooking, doing sports, birthday, etc. On the subject of traveling, the teacher will provide information on the importance of organizing a trip, what means of travel (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Khiva, London, New York) . This event serves to expand students' vocabulary and language abilities, broadening their worldview.

- riddles; Children love riddles. Because it is very interesting for them to find answers to riddles. Therefore, when the teacher tells the riddle in English or Uzbek, he should ask the children to answer it in English. Then children learn words quickly.

- practical activities (tasting vegetables, food and other products, smelling flowers); This sentence can be explained by the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "The pedagogue, who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory, should use as many of the child's sensory organs as possible: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscle sensations, and even if possible, he should try to involve the organs of smell and taste in the process of remembering". For example: when a teacher tastes an apple, its color is red or green, He should give information about the smell of whether it is sweet (tasty) or sour (), fragrant () and after feeding other students the fruits, he should ask the children to give information about that fruit in English.

- through gestures, facial expressions; When the teacher says something to the child or gives an order, for example, if the child uses gestures in sentences such as "come here", "open the book", "stand up", "look at the blackboard" will be clear.

- through visual aids, posters, books;

- writing on things that are visible and often used in everyday life. For example: writing on a door, book, table, blackboard, window, etc. learns words involuntarily due to falling into.

DISCUSSIONS

Today, an information base of a level that can meet the requirements of the time has been created, hypertext and multimedia, communication systems have been adopted. In 1956, N. V. Karpov and I. V. Rakhmanov's book "Methodology of foreign language teaching at the primary level" was published, and in this book it was said that technical means should be widely used in foreign language teaching to young children. Therefore, in teaching a foreign language, all didactic principles, that is, systematization, educational education, activity, demonstrativeness, consciousness, individual approach, thorough mastering, and the principles of compatibility, are inextricably linked to each other. will be implemented.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the purpose of teaching a foreign language to children of preschool educational organizations is to develop language skills of children through play. Teaching English to young children has its own characteristics. Children are very curious, they are quick to communicate, and because of their strong tendency to imitate, it is appropriate to teach them a language in a playful and non-committal manner. They are taught through repeated listening and as a result their speaking skills develop. We know that children's individual character and personality are developing during this period, so every method and approach used by the educator can have a positive effect on the child's development. It is effective to use modern methods and approaches in improving foreign language skills of preschool children.

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